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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	4
2. Current Hobs waste recovery treatment	5
3. WEEELoop Circular E-Waste system	7
3.1 Selective collection, classification and management. PROs.....	7
3.2 Recovery process in PRC nodes	8
4. WEEELoop economical projection	18
4.1 Key Financial Indicator	18
4.2 Cost Structure Analysis.....	18
4.3 Free Cash Flow.....	18
4.4 Profitability Analysis.....	19
5. Annex 1: Guidelines for the selection of waste for reuse at CPRs.	20
6. Annex 2: WEEELoop layout disposal	22
7. Annex 3: Recovery material images	23

1. Introduction

This document outlines the key process requirements for the treatment, recovery, and valorisation of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) and its components. It provides an overview of the definition protocols for the treatment and recovery of WEEE and recovered materials, focusing on methodologies that ensure the efficient treatment, classification, and recovery of materials. Emphasis is placed on their technical characteristics and potential applications, with the aim of maximising resource recovery while meeting environmental and regulatory standards.

The LIFE WEELOOP recovery process introduces multiple innovations compared to conventional WEEE treatment methods. In addition to employing advanced sorting and separation techniques, it integrates a more data-driven approach to optimise material recovery. One of its key differentiators is the use of the Circular AI platform, which enables structured data management and predictive analysis of waste patterns. This tool increases the efficiency of the recycling process by supporting better decision-making and optimised workflows. Another significant innovation is the development of more precise classification systems that enhance material purity and improve their potential for reuse in high-value applications.

A key component of this project is the development of the Circular Product Passport (CircPass), a digital tool designed to ensure traceability and transparency of recovered materials. While this document primarily addresses the methodologies and technologies applied in the early phases of material recovery—such as collection, sorting, and initial processing—the CircPass will be developed progressively throughout the project. It will gradually become an integral part of the management and documentation of recovered materials, enhancing transparency across the entire recovery chain.

By engaging key stakeholders—including extended producer responsibility organisations (PROs, *sistemas de responsabilidad ampliada del productor* in Spanish), WEEE management facilities, regulatory bodies and manufacturers—and optimising workflows, the LIFE WEELOOP treatment and recovery process lays the foundation for sustainable practices aligned with the principles of the circular economy. It bridges the gap between waste management and green production, supporting the transition to a more sustainable and resource-efficient future.

2. Current Hobs waste recovery treatment

Current circular economy models in the electrical and electronic equipment sector still face significant inefficiencies. Despite efforts to enhance the recovery, reuse, and recycling of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), existing environmental objectives are not fully achieved, especially with respect to the recovery of valuable components or the preparation for reuse of materials and components. This is to some extent due to a lack of integration among the different stakeholders in the value chain, limiting the full potential of recovered materials. To improve profitability, sustainability, and consumer value, new solutions are needed that go beyond conventional recycling approaches.

Figure 1 - Actual Hob recovery process

Currently, the recovery of hobs follows a standard process where waste materials are collected through various channels. This includes collection by producers or retailers when supplying or installing a new product (1:1 system), as well as drop-offs by installers or citizens at municipal collection points. In most cases, hobs are processed together with other waste from the same WEEE category (Category/FR 4: household domestic appliances larger than 50 cm). Producer Responsibility Organizations (PRO) such as ECOLEC in Spain, or independent waste treatment companies handle these processes, primarily due to the residual value of recovered materials.

The current recycling process for hobs follows these key steps:

- Separate collection of the hobs - along with other compatible WEEE - from the generation facilities; i.e., municipal collection points, retailers or producers mainly. This is performed by the systems managed by the PROs or directly by waste management companies. Conditions of the collected waste hobs vary differently depending of the origin of wastes based on aspects like cominglement with other wastes, containerization and handling procedures.
- Classification and Temporary storage: After collection, hobs are segregated and temporarily stored along with compatible wastes from the same Category (Category 4 of WEEE legislation) including washing machines or dishwashers in order to facilitate further processing.
- Identification and separation: The units are identified and separated based on their components and material composition.
- Dismantling and material recovery: At recycling plants, hobs are dismantled, and valuable materials such as plastics, functional electronic components, and recoverable metals (e.g., steel, aluminium, and copper) are extracted.
- Material segregation and resale: Once separated, these recovered materials are prepared for resale to manufacturers, contributing to a circular economy.

At present, most hobs undergo shredding and mechanical separation processes at recycling facilities. Physical techniques, including magnetic separation, Foucault currents, gravimetric sorting, and even image-based processing, may be employed to segregate different materials such as metals, glass, and plastics. However, these processes primarily focus on material recovery rather than the reuse of functional components. The conditions of the collected wastes, the lack of properly separated waste streams, and of the dedicated infrastructure, skilled technical personnel, and standardized procedures limits the potential for component recovery and reuse, highlighting the need for improved strategies that enhance circularity in the sector.

3. WEEELoop Circular E-Waste system

To overcome the limitations of the current recovery process, the LIFE WEEELOOP project introduces an innovative system aimed at maximizing the reuse of components from kitchen appliances. This new approach integrates advanced technologies, such as artificial vision for equipment identification and enhanced separation techniques, within specialized Preparation for Reuse Centres (PRCs).

The process begins with the collection of kitchen appliances, which are then sent to PRCs for further processing. At the Preparation for Reuse Centres, the waste undergoes a structured check-in process, where traceability labels are scanned, and the Digital Passport data is accessed to enhance traceability throughout the recovery process. It is at this stage that each hob is identified, and its components are assessed for potential reuse.

An artificial vision system, cross-referencing information with a database, recognizes each hob type and indicates which parts can be reused, repaired, or reconditioned. Advanced artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms analyse the brand and model, guiding operators through the extraction, inspection, and recovery of valuable components.

By implementing these technologies and structured processes, the project significantly improves component recovery efficiency, fostering sustainability and supporting the transition toward a circular economy.

3.1 Selective collection, classification and management. PROs

The collection of the waste hobs starts at the collection points, primarily municipal collection points, retailers, post-sale repair services or reverse logistics collected services. This is performed either by the systems managed by the PROs or directly by waste management companies.

If wastes are collected by waste management companies, these are in general not separated waste types and are used as feedstock to their recycling operations with the purpose of recovering valuable materials only.

When collected by the systems managed by the PROs, different types of WEEE are separately collected with the level of segregation performed at origin and transported either directly to final waste treatment facilities or to interim storage facilities. At these facilities, WEEE are classified in the different categories of compatible WEEE for separate processing on site or for further shipment to the authorized recycling or preparation for reuse facilities. According to Annex III of WEEE 2012/19/EU Directive as transposed to each MS legislation, waste hobs are stored separately along with compatible WEEE from “Category 4 Large equipment” with any external dimension of more than 50 cm, that covers most of large household appliances. This is the point where waste hobs can actually be segregated for preparation for reuse operations based on the criteria established in the guidelines developed as shown in [Annex 1](#), that include an analysis of the conditions of the waste hobs (e.g., complete, damaged, scavenged, etc.), suitability for the recovery of the materials and components and occupational health risks associated to the handling of the wastes.

Segregated waste hobs suitable for recovery operations should be properly conditioned for the safe and secure management and transportation, including the use of appropriate containers, and transported to the PRCs. PRCs may establish additional procedures for the selection and classification of the waste hobs received based on their own operational criteria.

3.2 Recovery process in PRC nodes

The recovery process within the node is divided into five key stages, each playing a vital role in ensuring the smooth flow and processing of materials. These stages include the creation of new records, check-in, entry certification, treatment, and treatment certification. Each stage is designed to handle the materials systematically, ensuring that all required actions are carried out efficiently and in compliance with established environmental and regulatory standards.

The node refers to a designated facility or operational unit where WEEE recovery activities take place, specifically the PRC. These centers integrate various processes and stakeholders involved in material processing and certification, serving as essential hubs for efficient and compliant recovery operations.

Figure 2 - Recovery process in PRC nodes

Throughout the process, materials progress through these stages in a structured manner, with each stage preparing the materials for the next phase. This systematic flow ensures proper tracking, management, and verification of the materials, enabling the team to monitor progress and make necessary adjustments as needed. To facilitate this, several layout options have been developed to visually represent how these stages are organized and interconnected.

To ensure the dismantling process operates efficiently, specific tools, equipment, layout designs, and personnel structures have been defined. The following sections outline these key components:

3.2.1 Necessary Tools and Equipment

The dismantling process requires a variety of tools and equipment to ensure efficiency and precision. The necessary tools include:

- Pneumatic Straight Screwdriver: With a torque range of approximately 0.4 to 3.5 Nm.
- Carbon Fibber Reaction Arm: For improved ergonomics (25Nm-940).
- Pneumatic Multi-Cutter: With a blade specifically for silicone cutting.
- Gas Welding Torch: For specific welding needs during the dismantling process.
- Retractable Weightless Balancer: To support the handling of tools and equipment.
- Assorted Screwdriver Bits: Includes Phillips, star, and Torx bits, as well as flat-head and hexagonal bits.
- Small Diameter Drill Bits: Specifically for removing rivets.
- Common Tools: Scissors, pliers, cutters, etc.
- Technology: Screen, CPU, camera, scale, etc.

These tools and equipment will be crucial in ensuring a smooth and effective dismantling process, allowing for both accuracy and safety.

3.2.2 Layout

A specific workstation layout has been developed for the team members working on the dismantling process. The layout ensures proper organization of materials and equipment, as well as an optimized workflow. Key components of the layout include:

- Material Segregation: The workstations will be equipped with appropriate containers for the types of materials generated during the dismantling process.
- CRIA System: Each station will be supported by the CRIA system, which provides guidance and oversight throughout the dismantling process.

The design is aimed at streamlining operations and improving the overall efficiency of the dismantling activity. A proposed layout diagram will further illustrate how these components are interconnected. Additional examples of layout configurations can be found in [Annex 2](#), providing further insights into the organization and workflow optimization.

Figure 3 – Possible layouts distribution and specifications.

3.2.3 Personnel

The personnel requirements estimation for the dismantling process are as follows:

- Total Work Hours: According to the collective agreement, the work hours total 1,776 hours per year.
- Daily Productivity: Estimated at 27.13 plates/day
- Annual Productivity: Estimated at approximately 6,000 plates/year per worker

The required personnel will depend on the actual flow of references to be processed. Given the current and projected conditions, a fully centralized approach is not feasible. Instead, a distributed processing model will be adopted, where operators handling a reasonable volume of countertop units will also be responsible for their dismantling. This approach ensures flexibility and efficiency based on actual demand.

- Check-In & Processing Personnel: Rather than assigning a dedicated check-in role, workers managing hobs units will also oversee their own intake and processing as needed.
- Material Handling: A material handler will facilitate the flow of incoming and outgoing materials, but the number of workstations will be adjusted dynamically to align with the volume of references being processed, avoiding unnecessary overcapacity.

In the following sections, we will delve into each stage in more detail, exploring the specific actions, requirements, and considerations for each one.

3.2.4 Process Stage Development

3.2.4.1 New register

The production process begins with the detailed registration of an incoming shipment. During this phase, batches of hobs from one or multiple PROs (Extended Producer Responsibility Schemes organizing Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Collection Systems) are received, weighed, and labelled to ensure precise control of the materials. This procedure guarantees proper documentation, facilitates traceability, and ensures that the hobs are prepared for the next stages of the specialized treatment process.

By implementing this step, the system ensures efficient material management from the start of the production cycle, which is crucial for the optimal recovery of components. Additionally, the software assigns a Pending Check-in status to the materials, indicating that they are awaiting verification before moving forward. This initial phase plays a critical role in tracking waste, ensuring compliance with regulations, and preparing the materials for further treatment and recycling.

3.2.4.2 Check in

The next step in the process is check-in, where the hobs are individually weighed, identified, and their detailed characteristics registered in Circular Replay's proprietary system, known as 'CRIA'. This system ensures comprehensive tracking of each unit, allowing for correct identification and classification. At this stage, the hobs are also labelled, following CRIA system guidelines, to facilitate their tracking throughout the entire production process.

Figure 4 - Recovery work table.

After check-in and labelling, the hobs are temporarily stored in a designated area before being transferred to a specialized cart or trolley, from where they will enter the component dismantling process. This step ensures an organized and efficient material flow throughout the production cycle.

At this point, the resulting status of this task is Pending Entry Certification, indicating that the hobs are awaiting certification of their entry into the system before proceeding to the next stage. At this point, the resulting status of this task is Pending Entry Certification, indicating that the hobs are awaiting certification of their entry into the system before proceeding to the next stage.

3.2.4.3 Entry certification

A key aspect of this project is ensuring reliable and accurate traceability throughout the process. Following the check-in stage, an incoming certification process is carried out with an external agent, specifically the PRO Management and Certification System from which the hobs originated. This step is critical in objectively verifying the received material and ensuring it meets the required standards for the treatment process.

The incoming certification process consists of reporting all kilograms received and rejected during transport. This data is submitted to the PRO platform, creating an accurate record of the received materials, including any discrepancies or rejections that may have occurred during shipment. The involvement of an external agent ensures authenticity, regulatory compliance, and transparency, reinforcing the ability to track and verify materials at every stage while ensuring they meet quality and environmental standards.

Once certification is complete, the material is ready for treatment. At this point, the resulting status is Pending Treatment, indicating that the hobs have been approved for processing and are waiting for the treatment stage to begin.

3.2.4.4 Treatment

The next stage in the process is treatment, where the hobs are dismantled on a specially designed workbench. The process begins with the identification of the hob using the label applied during the check-in phase. The hob is then positioned on the workbench, typically in an inverted position, before the dismantling tasks begin, assisted by the CRIA system, which guides the entire process.

The dismantling process takes place within a structured layout that includes distinct zones for receiving, dismantling, and waste classification. The process begins in the receiving zone, where the hobs undergo check-in and labelling. Once this step is complete, they are moved to the dismantling area, where the actual disassembly occurs.

As the dismantling progresses, the CRIA system assists in guiding the procedure, ensuring that materials suitable for reuse or specialized recycling are identified. The system cross-references the worktop models catalogued by CR & Copreci to determine items of interest, such as lighting fixtures, and recognizes glass components based on the customer's specifications. This automated guidance optimizes resource recovery, ensuring efficiency and responsible component reuse.

Once the treatment tasks are completed, the material is ready for certification. The resulting status of this task is Pending Treatment Certification, indicating that the hob has been processed and is awaiting verification before proceeding to the next stage.

Dismantling Assistance and Material Typology

The dismantling tasks begin with the assistance of the CRIA system, which is integrated into the process. This system is designed to guide the procedure, indicating which materials are suitable for reuse or specialized recycling, helping to streamline the workflow and ensure proper handling. As the system evolves, it will also identify the different types of materials to be classified for further processing. These materials will be categorized into three main types based on their recyclability and potential for reuse. The following outlines the typology of materials that the CRIA system is expected to identify during the dismantling process for their subsequent classification:

RESIDUE	SECONDARY RAW MATERIAL	COMPONENT
<p>These are materials commonly recycled for use in production processes across various sectors, with their sale to authorized waste managers being directly managed by CPR-E.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Wiring ▪ Aluminium ▪ Various Ferrous Metals ▪ Various Plastics ▪ PCB Recycling ▪ Sheet Metal ▪ Copper ▪ Residual Waste 	<p>This refers to the materials extracted from WEEE to be used in the production of new cooktops, partially or fully replacing the initial raw materials.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ceramic Glass 	<p>These are the elements that meet the specifications set by the recipient and, through a remanufacturing process, can be reused either in new cooktops or as replacement parts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ceramic Glass Panel for Reuse ▪ PCB for Reuse ▪ Radiant Heaters for Reuse ▪ Induction Heaters for Reuse

For the recycled or reuse decision, firstly, the registered references in the software database play a key role. The system automatically cross-checks whether a specific component is of interest for reuse, assisting the operator by flagging these elements and providing guidance on handling them with particular care. This helps prioritize components with higher reuse potential.

Second, the operator's expertise is essential in the final assessment. After the software highlights potential reusable components, the operator conducts a detailed inspection to verify their physical and functional condition. This includes checking for structural integrity, wear, and operational functionality. Based on this evaluation, the decision is made on whether the component is suitable for reuse or should be directed towards material recycling.

By combining digital traceability with human expertise, this process maximizes the recovery of valuable components, ensuring that functional elements are reintegrated into new products while non-reusable materials follow a responsible recycling route.

Material Classification for Recovery

The classification of materials recovered in recovery processes, categorized by material families, types, and specific denominations is shown in the following table. The table summarizes key information about these materials, distinguishing those to be recycled (SMR and RES) and those to be reused (COMP), along with their general applications. [Annex 3](#) contains pictures of each of the families registered in the recovery process. This overview provides a concise understanding of the materials and their classification, offering context without delving into detailed specifics.

FAMILY	TYPE OF MATERIAL	DENOMINATION
F1.1	SRM	Ceramic glass recycling
F1.2	COMP	Ceramic glass reuse
F2	RES	Wiring
F3	RES	Aluminium
F4	RES	Various ferrous metals
F5	RES	Various plastics
F6.1	RES	PCB recycling
F6.2	COMP	PCB reuse
F7.1	SRM	Radiant lamps recycling
F7.2	COMP	Radiant spotlights reuse
F8.1	RES	Inductor lamps recycling
F8.2	COMP	Inductor lamps reuse
F9	RES	Sheet metal
F10	RES	Copper
F11	RES	Rest

Material family description

F1.1-F1.2: CERAMIC GLASS: RECYCLING AND REUSE CATEGORIES

Ceramic glass is classified into two main categories based on its intended purpose: ceramic glass for recycling and ceramic glass for reuse. Each category has specific characteristics and criteria, as detailed below.

- Ceramic Glass: Recycling.** This category refers to ceramic glass fragments that, while suitable for recycling, do not meet the necessary specifications for direct reuse as ceramic glass. However, when processed according to specific guidelines, these fragments can be recycled to produce secondary raw materials for manufacturing new ceramic glass panels.

The selection criteria for recycling are based on two key factors: the predefined specifications for each reference (as defined and reflected in the software) and the operator's assessment to determine optimal recyclability. The general criteria include:

- Sorting Process Exclusion: Only glass fragments that do not meet the recovery criteria during the sorting process are considered.
- Black Vitroceramic Glass: Includes vitroceramic glass with colour characteristics suitable for recycling processes.

- Types and Sizes: A variety of vitroc ceramic glass types and sizes are acceptable if they comply with recycling standards.
- Brands and Manufacturers: Fragments from any appliance brand or manufacturer can be processed, as long as they align with recycling requirements.

These guidelines ensure that the ceramic glass fragments are selected based on established specifications and practical evaluation, facilitating efficient recycling into new ceramic glass panels.

The maximum allowable content of certain components or contaminants is as follows:

- **Ferrous Metals:** Less than 50 g/t.
- **Non-Ferrous Metals:** Less than 60 g/t.
- **Non-Vitroc ceramic Glass:** Less than 100 g/t (e.g., container glass, flat glass).
- **Transparent/White Ceramic Glass:** Less than 100 g/t.
- **Organics:** Less than 2000 g/t (e.g., silicone adhesive residues).
- **Ceramic Glass: Reuse** This category includes ceramic glass that meets the CRIA sorting specifications and is deemed suitable for reuse. The criteria for this category include:
 - Sorting Compliance: Glass that has successfully met the criteria during the sorting process for reuse purposes.
 - Complete and Undamaged Glass: Glass materials that are intact and show no visible damage.

Verification Process

The verification of compliance with these thresholds is carried out during the dismantling phase. The assessment is based on:

- Operator Evaluation: The dismantling operator visually inspects the material and applies predefined selection criteria.
- Software-Assisted Parameterization: The software provides reference specifications to support decision-making and ensure consistency in material classification.
- Basic Sorting Tools: Simple tools such as weight scales and visual inspection guidelines help confirm compliance with allowable contaminant levels.

This process ensures that both reuse and recycling decisions align with the material specifications and predefined sorting parameters.

F2 – F5: DIFFERENT TYPES OF RESIDUES.

These categories cover different types of material, including wiring, aluminium, ferrous metals, and plastics, each with unique characteristics and recovery processes. The recovery of these materials involves a combination of software-assisted identification and manual separation.

- **Wiring:** Wiring waste refers to remnants or discarded materials from electrical cables, which contain copper-based by-products. As previously mentioned, the recovery process begins with visual inspection and functional testing to determine the suitability for reuse. The software assists in identifying the materials suitable for recovery, while the operator manually separates the copper-based materials for further processing and reuse.
- **Aluminium:** Aluminium scrap consists of non-ferrous metal materials, identifiable by their lack of magnetic properties. The recovery of aluminium follows a similar approach, with the software helping to identify aluminium components and the operator manually separating them based on material characteristics.

- **Various Ferrous Metals:** Ferrous metal scrap includes iron-based materials, identifiable by their magnetic properties. As with other materials, the software assists in identifying suitable ferrous metal scrap, and the operator manually separates and categorizes these materials for recycling.
- **Various Plastics:** Plastic waste comprises materials made from polymer plastics such as PP, ABS, PPS, or PA. The recovery process for plastics involves a thorough preparation phase, where metal insertions, such as screws, washers, or wires, are manually removed by the operator. The software assists in identifying only those free of impurities proceed to recycling. The operator, with specialized training and expertise, ensures the proper removal of contaminants and the classification of plastics according to their type, making them suitable for the recycling stream.

F6.1 - F6.2: PRINTED CIRCUIT BOARDS

Printed circuit boards (PCBs) are critical components of electronic devices, and their end-of-life management plays a significant role in sustainable recycling practices. Whether designated for recycling or reuse, the handling of PCBs requires careful consideration to maximize resource recovery and minimize waste.

Recycling focuses on extracting valuable materials from boards no longer suitable for reuse, while reuse involves the inspection and repurposing of functional PCBs. The software plays a key role in determining whether a PCB can be reused by analysing its components and identifying those suitable for recovery. When the software detects a PCB with reusable elements, it alerts the operator, who, following specialized training and handling procedures, carefully extracts the identified components. This ensures that only functional parts are recovered, while the remaining materials are directed to recycling. Together, these processes contribute to reducing environmental impact and promoting the principles of the circular economy by extending the lifecycle of electronic components and enabling the creation of secondary raw materials.

- **PCB Recycling:** Printed circuit boards (PCBs) designated for recycling include power boards, filter boards, and touch panels that have reached the end of their useful life or are deemed unsuitable for reuse. As previously explained, the software assists in identifying boards that are no longer functional, guiding the operator in determining their recyclability. These boards are then processed to recover valuable materials such as metals and other components. In the case of power boards, it is essential to separate the aluminium heat sink from the PCB before proceeding with the recycling process. This ensures efficient recovery of materials and supports the creation of secondary raw materials for other industries.
- **PCB Reuse:** PCBs identified for reuse are specific circuit boards that retain functionality and meet the criteria for reuse as spare parts or integration into new devices. As previously mentioned, the software analyses the condition of the PCB and identifies components suitable for recovery. When a reusable PCB is detected, the software alerts the operator, who, following specialized training and careful handling procedures, extracts and prepares the board for future applications. By prioritizing reuse where possible, this approach aligns with circular economy principles and extends the lifecycle of electronic components.

F7.1-F7.2, F8.1-F8.2: RADIANT AND INDUCTION ELEMENTS: RECYCLING AND REUSE

Radiant and induction elements, crucial components in various electronic devices, can be classified based on their end-of-life status and potential for recycling or reuse. This process is carried out by the operator with the support of specialized software, which assists in the visual inspection and functional testing phases. The visual inspection assesses the condition of each element, while the functional testing verifies key operational aspects. Based on these evaluations, elements that pass both stages are deemed suitable for reuse, while those that do not are categorized for recycling.

- **Radiant Elements: Recycling:** Radiant elements that have reached the end of their useful life and are unsuitable for reuse fall under this category. These components, commonly found in heating systems or cooktops, are processed based on established recycling specifications. The process focuses on the separation of materials, classifying them according to their potential interest for final stakeholders. This includes extracting materials through classification and returning them to the manufacturers for further use. By recovering valuable materials such as metals and insulating components, these radiant elements contribute to the generation of secondary raw materials, supporting sustainable practices in the electronics industry.
- **Radiant Elements: Reuse:** Some radiant elements remain in good condition and meet the criteria for reuse. These components are visually inspected and assessed by the operator, taking into account those references defined as optimal for circularity (criteria incorporated into the software). After this, they undergo the necessary functional tests, which cover basic aspects of functionality such as the cable connections, the radiant itself, and other essential components to ensure proper operation. Once certified, these reusable radiant elements can be reintegrated into other hobs, reducing the need for new raw materials and extending the lifecycle of existing components.
- **Induction Elements: Recycling:** Induction elements that have reached the end of their operational life and are no longer suitable for reuse are classified for recycling. These components, typically found in advanced cooktops and heating systems, consist of materials such as copper coils, ferrite cores, and insulating layers. During the recycling process, valuable materials like copper are extracted and repurposed, while non-recoverable materials are responsibly classified and processed in the most efficient way possible. This responsible classification ensures that all materials are sorted properly, maximizing the recovery of valuable resources and minimizing the environmental impact of the waste. By carefully handling and processing these materials, we contribute to the sustainability of electronic manufacturing processes and promote a more circular economy.
- **Induction Elements: Reuse:** Induction elements, which play a critical role in modern cooktops, can also be eligible for reuse. Specific induction elements that meet functional and quality standards are retained for reuse, offering the same benefits as radiant elements in terms of sustainability and resource efficiency. These components can be directly incorporated into new products or used as spare parts, showcasing the importance of circular economy principles in managing electronic waste.

F9-F11: OTHER TYPE OF RESIDUES:

The recycling process for waste materials encompasses not only well-defined categories such as wiring, plastics, and metals but also a diverse range of mixed and residual materials. These materials, often composed of complex combinations of metallic and non-metallic components, present unique challenges and opportunities for recycling. By addressing these waste streams, the recycling process ensures that no valuable resources are left unutilized, contributing to the broader goals of sustainability and material recovery.

Key categories within this domain include mixed metal and non-metallic waste, copper and copper-based materials, and general residual waste. Each of these waste streams is handled manually, with the operator visually sorting and identifying recyclable materials. The specialization comes from the operator's learning curve, which allows them to efficiently identify materials for recovery and separate those that are not of interest or reusable over time.

The classification and processing of residual waste are further guided by the material parameterization within the software, which defines whether a material can be recycled, reused, or classified as waste. While most incoming materials can be recovered, certain elements that do not meet the required

criteria are designated as non-recyclable waste and directed to appropriate disposal streams. The following sections explore the characteristics, processing, and recycling pathways for these materials, highlighting their importance in achieving a circular economy.

- **Mixed Metal and Non-Metallic Waste: Recycling.** This category encompasses waste materials which consist of mixed fragments of metals such as iron, copper, and aluminum, as well as non-metallic materials attached to or containing metals. These materials, not falling under previously defined categories, are designated for shredding and subsequent recycling. Examples include fans, screws, and base assemblies of inductive elements made from plastic or aluminum with ferrite components. Additionally, terminal block assemblies and other similar items fall within this classification.
- **Copper and Copper-Based Materials: Recycling.** Copper scrap primarily originates from the litz wire of inductive elements and other copper-based components. These materials, known for their high recyclability, are segregated and processed to recover pure copper for reuse in manufacturing.
- **Residual Waste: Recycling (Rest).** Residual waste includes fragments of various metals and non-metallic materials that do not fall under other specific categories. These materials, such as plastic, rubber, insulation, and adhesives combined with metal fragments, undergo processing to facilitate recycling. Depending on their composition and recovery potential, some of these materials may be shredded to improve handling and separation before further treatment.

This structured approach ensures that resource recovery is maximized while appropriately managing non-recoverable materials.

3.2.5 Treatment certification

The final stage in the process involves the certification of the treatment, ensuring that all procedures have been completed according to the required standards. This phase verifies that the materials have undergone the appropriate processing and comply with the specifications for reuse, recycling, or disposal.

The verification process is carried out using the software, which generates a report detailing all the worktops processed and successfully closed in the shipment. This report specifies how many kilograms are designated for reuse, recycling, or disposal. This information is then submitted to the PRO platform, where it is used to obtain the treatment certification.

Similar to the entry certification, the treatment certification is conducted on the PRO platform, but in this case, it focuses on certifying the dismantling of each shipment. The system verifies the kilograms of material recycled and reused, ensuring that the mass balance aligns with the total input weight and that the treatment has been performed in an environmentally responsible manner. This step is crucial for maintaining reliable traceability throughout the entire process, confirming that every action in the treatment phase is well-documented and compliant with regulatory standards.

Once the treatment certification is completed, the process is considered concluded. At this point, the resulting state of the task is finalized, marking the successful completion of the entire treatment cycle and the readiness of the material for the next steps in its lifecycle.

4. WEEELoop economical projection

The economic projections of the LIFE WEEELOOP project are based on the financial estimates registered in the Grant Agreement. These projections outline the cost structure, free cash flow expectations, and profitability analysis associated with the initiative. Given that this is a public document, the focus is on key financial indicators that reflect the viability and sustainability of the model without disclosing excessive financial details.

4.1 Key Financial Indicator

To evaluate the economic feasibility of the project, several financial indicators have been considered:

- **Cost Structure:** Distribution of costs related to the production process, including materials, operational expenses, and administrative costs.
- **Free Cash Flow (FCF):** Represents the net cash generated by the project after covering operational costs and investments.
- **Profitability Metrics:** Analysis of revenue generation, payback period, and return on investment (ROI).
- **Net Present Value (NPV):** The present value of projected future cash flows, assessing the long-term viability of the investment.
- **Internal Rate of Return (IRR):** The expected rate of return based on estimated project revenues and costs.

By leveraging these indicators, the financial assessment provides a structured approach to evaluating the economic impact and long-term sustainability of the project.

4.2 Cost Structure Analysis

During the LIFE project, the Cost of Goods Sold (COGS) associated with consortium partners and directly related to the innovation action is absorbed by them. After the project, these costs are estimated to represent approximately 45% of the selling price of products. These costs are expected to remain stable due to consortium agreements and efficiencies gained through process industrialization.

Similarly, Selling, General, and Administrative (SG&A) expenses required for reclaimed product production are estimated at 60% during the project. However, due to upscaling and process efficiencies, they are projected to decrease to 40% after the project's completion. These reductions in costs highlight the potential for improved economic performance through increased operational efficiency.

4.3 Free Cash Flow

The project's financial forecast includes an aggregated cash flow analysis, considering the supply of reutilized hob components and materials, as well as the production of sustainable cooktops. Projections indicate that cash flow will initially be negative due to investment costs but will improve as economies of scale are achieved. The financial model incorporates funding from grants to mitigate early-stage negative cash flows, ensuring the project's financial stability.

4.4 Profitability Analysis

Revenues generated from the sale of components, materials, and eco-designed cooktops during the project's first three years are expected to reach a significant percentage of total funding. However, initial negative cash flows are anticipated due to the required investment in infrastructure and process development.

The payback period for the investment, considering no grant, is projected to be more than six years. However, with a grant covering 60% of project costs, this period is reduced to approximately five years. The Net Present Value (NPV) of cash flows over six years indicates that, with grant support, the project maintains a positive financial outlook. Similarly, the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) significantly improves with grant support, reinforcing the economic viability of the model.

These financial indicators, aligned with the assumptions in the Grant Agreement, demonstrate the project's potential profitability and sustainability. However, external factors such as market trends and supply-demand fluctuations may influence final outcomes, as outlined in the project's risk management strategy.

5. Annex 1: Guidelines for the selection of waste for reuse at CPRs.

A non-exhaustive list of examples is shown for illustrative purposes to help identify the worktops requested to be sent to CPR Specialised. The aim is to avoid sending unsolicited waste, which could cause risks to workers involved in the processes or inefficiencies in the system.

If the collection centre has doubts about the appropriateness of sending it to the specialised CPR, the waste will be sent to a plant for decontamination and recycling.

Description	Example	Pictures
Examples of waste requested to be sent to Specialised CPR		
Induction and radiant hobs	Palletising shrink-wrapping/stretch wrapping	
Induction hobs	With black glass, incandescent lamps	
Radiant glass ceramic hobs	With black glass, radiant spotlights	
Worktops with surface damage	With scratched/slightly broken glass	

Description	Example	Pictures
Examples of waste not requested to be sent to Specialised CPR		
Improper waste (not worktop)	Oven	
Unmanageable residue (worktop leftovers)	Worktop with shards of broken glass that may pose risks to CPR operators.	
Unmanageable residue (worktop leftovers)	Worktop glass assembly without elements recoverable for reuse.	
Gas hobs	Gas cooker with burners (black and white version)	
Induction hobs with white glass	Worktop with white glass	

6. Annex 2: WEEELoop layout disposal

7. Annex 3: Recovery material images

Family	Type of material	Denomination	Pictures
F1.1	SRM	Ceramic glass recycling	
F1.2	COMP	Ceramic glass reuse	
F2	RES	Wiring	
F3	RES	Aluminium	
F4	RES	Various ferrous metals	
F5	RES	Various plastics	

Family	Type of material	Denomination	Pictures
F6.1	RES	PBC recycling	
F6.2	COMP	PBC reuse	
F7.1	SRM	Radiant lamps recycling	
F7.2	COMP	Radiant lamps reuse	
F8.1	RES	Inductor lamps recycling	
F8.2	COMP	Inductor lamps reuse	

Family	Type of material	Denomination	Pictures
F9	RES	Sheet metal	
F10	RES	Copper	
F11	RES	Rest	